

Analysis of Unmetered Coordination in the *Tōgaku* Ensemble of Japanese Court Music (*Gagaku*)

Martin Clayton and Sayumi Kamata

In this paper we explore empirically the organization of instrumental *gagaku* music in unmetered or free rhythm sections, comparing this with metrical organization in the same genre. The term *gagaku* 雅楽 refers to the entire body of classical music and dance that has been performed in the Japanese imperial court, and this paper focuses on *tōgaku* 唐楽, a subset of instrumental ensemble music that comprises a large proportion of the *gagaku* repertoire. The *tōgaku* repertoire includes, alongside pieces organized with reference to clear metrical structures (Kamata and Clayton 2025), others apparently without any meter, known as *jobuki* 序吹. The organization of this music—composed, with a clear formal organization and the coordination of up to eight different parts, but apparently unmetered—has not been discussed in any depth in the musicological literature. This may be partly because their organization is even less explicitly described through notation and description than that of metrical pieces, and is even more dependent on musicians’ practical knowledge. Using empirical analysis of a published set of audiovisual recordings, the aim of this paper is both to extend research on performance practice of *gagaku* into these *jobuki* sections, and to develop that on unmetered or “free” rhythm to consider forms involving significant ensemble coordination.

[2] The instruments of the *tōgaku* ensemble can be grouped into three classes: wind, string and percussion (see Fig. 1 and Table 1). Previous studies of contemporary *gagaku* performance have indicated that the winds are responsible for the main melody and, particularly in metrical pieces, the strings “trace the melody while clearly indicating the beats” and the percussion instruments “set the tempo and rhythm of the piece by creating a series of rhythmic patterns” (e.g., Endō 2013). Three prominent characteristics relating to its time organization have been highlighted are: (a) the gradual acceleration observed as a piece progresses (Shōno 1987, Terauchi 2011); (b) a markedly drawn-out interval between the last beat of the measure and the first beat of the next (Garfias 1975, Nelson 2008); and (c) deliberately “loose” synchrony in the ensemble (Kamata and Clayton 2025). As a result of these features, it may be quite difficult for those who have never heard *gagaku* before to immediately recognize its metrical structure from a performance.

Figure 1. Layout of instruments (drawn by Sayumi Kamata)

<i>Section</i>	<i>Instrument (left to right)</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Wind</i>	Ryūteki 龍笛	transverse bamboo flute
	Hichiriki 篳篥	short double-reed pipe
	Shō 笙	free-reed mouth organ
<i>String</i>	Koto (<i>Sō, Gakusō</i>) 箏 (樂箏)	13-stringed long zither
	Biwa 琵琶	four-stringed lute
<i>Percussion</i>	Shōko 鈺鼓	dish-shaped gong
	Taiko 太鼓	large suspended drum
	Kakko 鞆鼓	small barrel drum

Table 1. Instruments of the *tōgaku* ensemble

[3] The above discussions are based on examples from metrical-formal pieces,¹ and non-metrical *jobuki* pieces are only briefly mentioned. The main reason why the discussion so far has concentrated on metrical examples appears to be that, in the central repertoire of some eighty suites of *tōgaku*, only eight suites (Shunnōden 春鶯囀, Konju 胡飲酒, Goshōraku 五常樂, Kishunraku 喜春樂, Sokō 蘇合香, Manjuraku 萬秋樂, Somakusha 蘇莫者 and Sanju 散手) contain examples of consistently non-metrical pieces. However, contrary to the impression given by the small proportion of non-metrical pieces, *tōgaku* performances typically feature both metrical and non-metrical rhythms. Introductory pieces—which are always played at the beginning of a performance before the suite proper—are non-metrical, and in some instances, non-metrical sections are included at the beginning or end of the metrical sections of the main piece. It is essential to consider both metrical and non-metrical aspects when exploring the temporal organization and coordination in *gagaku* performance practice.

1. By metrical-formal we intend a formal organisation built on metrical structure (e.g., sections comprise specific numbers of measures).

[4] While non-metrical rhythms in instrumental ensembles are often described in the historical literature as “*jobuki*,” it should be noted that the term does not refer to the rhythms themselves, but rather refers to the act of blowing of the wind instruments.² Previous studies have simply labelled them as “free rhythm” (Garfias 1975, Endō 2013, Nelson 2008) or “non-metrical” (Gamō 1987, Terauchi 1996, Terauchi 2011); researchers who use the latter term may have wanted to avoid giving the impression that *jobuki* pieces are free from formal constraints. This is probably because the multilayered structure, which has been noted as a characteristic of Japanese music as a whole—where multiple phrases or rhythmic units form cohesive units, which in turn come together to form larger units, thereby shaping the overall structure (Yokomichi 1986, 15)—is also observed in the composition of *jobuki*.

[5] The differences between non-metrical and metrical rhythms, as manifested in the notation used by contemporary performers, are illustrated using the *hichiriki* part as an example (Figs 2 and 3). Both pieces are marked with large drum strokes (large black circles) corresponding to the convergence points of all instrument phrases, but in Fig. 3 the number of symbols in each span is constant, whereas in Fig. 2 it is not. If looking through the notation of the whole piece, one will find repetitions of phrases within the arrangement of symbols (such as those highlighted here in blue, green and yellow) and may observe how small units are stacked up to form successively larger units in constituting the musical structure. Sukehiro Shiba (1898–1982), a *gagaku* performer, also recognized this structural property early on, transnotating almost all current pieces into staff notation, analyzing and classifying musical formulae based on the *ryūteki* melodies (Shiba 1967–72; see Fig. 4 for an example of this notation). However, the three features that characterize the rhythm—gradual acceleration, a markedly extended interval before the first beat of a measure, and deliberately “loose” synchrony—are not reflected in either the performer's notation or the stave transcription, as these are all performance conventions. In other words, there is a limit to what can be learned from such documentation alone, which is why an analysis of audiovisual data is crucial.

2. The character “序 *jo*” means “beginning,” “sequence,” “order,” etc., but does not explicitly include the concept of non-metrical rhythm; according to Terauchi (1996:18), terms such as “序吹 *jobuki*” and “序弾 *jobiki*” are clearly derived from the name of the piece “Jo”, which is based on non-metrical rhythm. However, not all non-metrical pieces are necessarily marked with the character “序.” The character “吹,” read as *fuku*, *sui*, etc., means “to blow (sound an instrument).”

Figure 2. *Hichiriki* performance notation until the first four strong *taiko* beats of a non-metrical piece “Jo,” based on the sets of official standard notations digitally published under the title “Gagakufu” but generally known as “Meiji sentei-fu” (“Selected Scores of Meiji”), of 1876 and 1888. (<https://doi.org/10.20730/100270332>), Transcribed by Sayumi Kamata to fit into one figure.

The notation is read down the vertical columns starting from the right; the large characters are the *shōga* mnemonic syllables which represent notes on the *hichiriki*³, with small characters to the left showing fingerings. A large black circle is marked to the right of where the large drum stroke enters, which is in columns 1, 3, 4 and 6. It is evident that the number of *shōga* syllables per *taiko* span, i.e., the length of the phrase up to the point where all instruments converge, is not constant. Annotations have been added to indicate repeated phrases of the *hichiriki* (blue, green and yellow highlights) and each *taiko* span (red brackets)

3. An oral mnemonic system known as *shōga* 唱歌 (literally meaning “singing song”) is an indispensable means for grasping the melodic details and the flow of the music as a whole, as a musician’s learning process begins with *shōga* in one of the wind instruments.

Figure 3. *Hichiriki* performance notation of the first four cycles (including the first four strong taiko beats) of a metrical piece “Juha.” This example shows one metrical cycle written on a single column, with a large black circle to the right of the *shōga* mnemonic syllables containing the large *taiko* stroke, and a small black dot to the right of the syllables that correspond to the beginning of the other bars. There is approximately the same amount of *shōga* syllables in each cycle.

Annotations have been added to indicate repeated phrases of the *hichiriki* (blue and yellow highlights) and *taiko* cycles (red brackets)

[6] Clayton proposed a definition of “free rhythm” as “the rhythm of music without pulse-based periodic organization” (1996, 329), roughly equating “free” with “unmetered.” As he noted at the time, many examples of “free” or “unmetered” rhythm can be identified around the world. Examples of such music can be found in forms of religious chant, such as Persian *avaaz* (Tsuge 1978, Reckford 1987, Ohriner 2016) or Jewish *nusah* (Frigyesi 1993), as laments (e.g., Tolbert 1988), or as soloistic melodic

traditions such as Indian alap (Widdess 1994), or Turkish/Arabic taksim (Holzapfel 2013, Cholevas 2017, Roeder 2019, Abramovay 2025). There is a small but significant analytical literature on some of these genres.

[7] London's description of meter as a "musically-specific form of entrainment, the synchronization of attention and/or other behaviors... with periodic rhythms in the environment" (2012, 9) suggests that "unmetered" forms lack, or eschew, the kind of regularity in the music's time organization that would allow such entrainment. The perception of meter is an active process and it is possible that any element of temporal stability or predictability, even if unintended or short-lived, might give rise to a percept of beat or meter in some listeners; thus, the labels "metrical" and "free" cannot be considered a simple binary. It is clear from the literature that "free rhythm" forms may not be entirely free of metrical elements, but elements of pulse or even meter may be observed: either intermittent, present in the mind of the performer but not made explicit in the sound (Widdess 1994), or perceived by listeners even if not intended by performers or objectively present in the sound (Will et al 2015). Such rhythm may be related to the rhythms of speech, or to those of poetic forms which are rendered in song (Tsuge 1978, Reckford 1987). While Ohriner attempts to bring free rhythm within the framework of entrainment theory (2016), Roeder applies to the phenomenon Hasty's notion of "projection," which like entrainment is concerned with expectations of temporal regularities based on previous events, but is less closely aligned with the idea of metrical structure (Hasty 1997, Roeder 2019).

[8] While some of these ideas may be applicable to *jobuki* rhythm, none of this literature tackles the key question addressed by the present paper, which is *how the gagaku ensemble is coordinated temporally in the absence of metrical structure*. Even if many of the forms of free-rhythm music previously analyzed may be performed by more than one person, whether in turn or overlapping, the coordination of multiple, distinct instrumental parts in the *jobuki* sections of *gagaku* seems to present a distinct case, one which has not previously been subject to detailed analytical study. We therefore explore the temporal organization of *jobuki* sections of a *tōgaku* suite using empirical analysis of audiovisual recordings; comparison between non-metrical *jobuki* pieces and metrical pieces is used to highlight the particular features of the former.

METHODS

Dataset

[9] The subject of analysis here is a set of recordings of the *tōgaku* (literally, “music of the [Chinese] Tang [dynasty]”) suite Shunnōden, recorded by an eight-piece instrumental ensemble. Audiovisual recordings and accompanying annotations are published separately (Clayton, Kamata, Takaoka & Tarsitani 2023). The recorded material includes “Ichikotsuchō no Chōshi 壹越調調子,” the introductory piece for playing in the *Ichikotsuchō* mode (which is roughly analogous to a mixolydian mode on D), and the *tōgaku* suite “Shunnōden 春鶯囀,” literally “The Warbler Sings in the Spring.” In its full form, Shunnōden consists of six pieces—Yūsei 遊声, Jo 序, Sattō 颯踏, Juha 入破, Tesshō 鳥声 and Kisshō 急声—and falls into the most prestigious *taikyoku* 大曲 category, which includes structurally complex compositions and the combination of non-metrical and metrical rhythms. The focus of this analysis is the *jobuki* sections of Shunnōden, namely “Yūsei,” “Jo,” “Tesshō,” and the last part of “Kisshō” (see Table 2), although extensive comparison will also be made with the metrical sections of the suite.

[10] In our corpus, transcriptions of interviews with some of the performing musicians are also published with audiovisual recordings and annotations. Specifically, interviews were conducted with *ryūteki* player Takuya Kōketsu, *hichiriki* player Motonori Miura and *shō* player, Junko Yatsuki.⁴ *Gagaku* performers join the ensemble in various roles depending on the occasion, so it was possible to ask questions about the parts other than the wind instruments. As these musicians’ comments on how they perceive *gagaku* performance have already been detailed elsewhere (Kamata and Clayton 2025), the results presented below focus specifically on their comments on *jobuki* and the contrast between metrical and non-metrical sections within the suite.

4. Biographical sketches of the three interviewees can be found in the Appendix.

Piece	Meter/ <i>Jobuki</i>	Structure	Recording
1_Ichikotsuchō no Chōshi 壱越調調子	<i>Jobuki</i> (no <i>taiko</i>)		2 takes
2-7_Gagaku Suite “Shunnōden” 春鶯囀			
2_Yūsei 遊声	<i>Jobuki</i> (no <i>taiko</i>)	A – B – C – B – C – B	2 takes
3_Jo 序	<i>Jobuki</i> (“hyōshi-jūroku” 拍子十六 16 strong notes on the <i>taiko</i>)	A – B – C – B’	1 take
4_Sattō 颯踏	Metrical (“haya-ya-hyōshi hyōshi-jūroku” 早八拍子 拍子十六 8 bars ⁵ of 4/4 make up one rhythmic cycle, which is repeated 16 times)	A – B – C – B’	1 take
5_Juha 入破	Metrical (“haya-mu-hyōshi hyōshi-jūroku” 早六拍子 拍子十六 6 bars of 4/4 make up one rhythmic cycle, which is repeated 16 times)	A – B – C – B’	1 take
6_Tesshō 鳥声	<i>Jobuki</i> (“hyōshi-jūroku” 拍子十六 16 strong notes on the <i>taiko</i>)	A – A – A’ – A’ – B	2 takes

5. It is commonly understood among musicians and researchers that the rhythmic unit called “kobyōshi” in Japanese corresponds to a bar/measure (Shiba 1971, Nelson 2008, Terauchi 2011), and we follow this convention.

7_Kisshō 急声	Metrical (“haya-mu-hyōshi hyōshi-jūroku” 早六拍子 拍子十六 6 bars of 4/4 make up one rhythmic cycle, which is repeated 16 times); plus final section of <i>Jobuki</i> (with <i>taiko</i>)	A – B – C – B' - coda	1 take (continuous after second take of Tesshō)
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Table 2. Outline of the suite Shunnōden, recordings and metrical structure.

[11] Our annotation of the performances loosely follows Shiba’s approach (1967–72) in breaking the main Sections (A, B, C etc.) into Sentences (a1, a2, b1 etc.); each Sentence includes one to three melodic phrases articulated by the wind instruments.⁶ Based on this documentation, our empirical analysis of the audiovisual recordings sheds light on temporal features of the music as performed that are not reflected in the extant notations.

6. Shiba's division is modelled on seven levels of hierarchy, from the smallest unit “gakusei” to the whole piece “gakushō:” In his explanation of the hierarchical model, a unit of a structural level consists of two or more units of the lower levels. However, his analytical examples also include cases where a piece is divided in the same way on two adjacent levels. This may be partly due to the fact that gagaku pieces vary in length and include short pieces that are not suitable for the seven-level subdivision. Our sectional divisions correspond to the fourth “gakusetsu” and/or fifth “gakudan” levels listed by Shiba, depending on the piece.

[12] The audiovisual data comprises multitrack audio (one microphone for each of the eight instruments) and video recordings (five cameras). The recordings were manually annotated as follows in order to generate timing data for the empirical analysis:

- i. Structural divisions (as described above, referring to Shiba’s analysis of hierarchical levels)
- ii. In the case of metrical pieces, each measure
- iii. Start and end points of each wind phrase (*ryūteki* and *hichiriki*)

[13] Event onsets were marked up for the string and percussion instrument tracks using a custom onset detection script in Matlab (Eerola et al 2018); the output of this process was subject to manual checking and editing. In the wind instrument tracks, “onsets” were taken as the points at which new stable pitches are reached—either at the start of a phrase or in the middle of a phrase following ornaments. These wind “onsets” were marked up manually in Sonic Visualiser. It should be noted, however, that the “onsets” of the *shō* part were not marked because they were obscured in the audio recording by the volume of the *hichiriki* part (the *hichiriki* and *shō* players sit next to one another). Empirical analysis was carried out in RStudio, with packages used including onsetsync (Eerola & Clayton 2024) and WaveletComp (Rosch & Schmidbauer 2018).

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

[14] In order to explore the structure of the music, including the possible presence of periodic elements—both in continuous sound durations and in intervals between events—we carried out a series of analytical processes on the dataset described above.

Visual Inspection of Synoptic Event Plots of Each Section

[15] Complementing the visual representation of Shiba in score form, we explore the structure of the music by visualizing events (onsets) and durations (wind phrases) alongside the Sentence boundaries, without having to make arbitrary decisions over rhythmic values. Where two takes are available of the same piece, we compare the two takes visually, in order to distinguish consistent aspects of the structure from accidental alignments between events and parts. (This is the case for “Yūsei” and “Tesshō,” two of the three most substantial *jobuki* sections.) This helps to clarify aspects of the rhythmic

structure of the piece as a whole and the relationships between instrumental parts which are not revealed by the part-by-part notation currently used by performers, or by Shiba's transcription alone. *Jobuki* and metrical pieces are compared to highlight the special features of the former.

Analysis Of Wind Phrase Durations

[16] In the second phase of analysis, we explore the *hichiriki* and *ryūteki* phrases by plotting phrase duration against time and calculating the proportion of time each instrument is playing for each piece. We know from the interview data that these players are focused on the individual characteristics of phrasing associated with their particular instrument (discussed in detail below). Therefore, we explore the hypothesis that—in the absence of metrical structure—the time taken by the wind players to perform the melodic phrases is one of the main drivers of the temporal structure of the music. We look again at comparisons between takes and compare phrase durations in *jobuki* pieces with the metrical pieces.

Onset Interval Analysis

[17] In the third phase of analysis, we consider also the percussion and string sections. These instruments are played using strikes and plucks; thus the timing of event onsets is an important element of their contribution to temporal structure, although as noted in Kamata & Clayton (2025), preparatory movements offer an element of continuous timing data to complement these moments.⁷ This analysis has two parts:

- i. We analyze each percussion and string instrument in turn, looking for evidence of periodicity (consistency of interval durations) and/or acceleration, comparing results for *jobuki* and metrical pieces.
- ii. We combine “onset” data for all instruments (including *ryūteki* and *hichiriki* but not *shō*, where we do not have reliable data) and explore periodic

7. By ‘preparatory’ movements we refer to movements made in preparation of sounding an instrument, which in many cases are deliberate and closely controlled by the performer.

components using wavelet transform analysis,⁸ again comparing *jobuki* and metrical pieces.

RESULTS

Interviews

[18] Before describing our analysis of the audiovisual recordings, relevant information on how these musicians feel about *jobuki* is summarised here.⁹ When we asked the musicians to talk about the recorded suite “Shunnōden,” the contrast between metrical and non-metrical *jobuki* sections was mentioned in all the interviews. A common emphasis of the interviewees was that the feeling was “totally different” between metrical and *jobuki* pieces (Yatsuki 00:21:03), and that the latter is more challenging. Although they can participate in the ensemble playing different instruments, the challenges of playing *jobuki* were mainly discussed from the perspective of the wind players.

[19] According to *shō* player Yatsuki, both the metrical and non-metrical sections may seem difficult from the outside, but the former can be “surprisingly viable” if a sense of beat and the flow of the music is not disturbed. In the latter, however, the *shō* may have to precede other wind phrases in some pieces, or may have to respond to the expansion or contraction of other wind phrases—in other words, wind instruments have a wider range of flexibility in *jobuki*, so it is necessary to “establish” one's own playing style and at the same time have “extra energy to cope” with the other parts. In particular, to coordinate

8. The wavelet transform is a method for decomposing a signal into several components at different frequency/ period bands. Analogous to the Fourier transform in this respect, it has advantages when identifying periodic components which are localised, i.e., that do not persist throughout the signal. As Toivianen and Hartmann put it, “The [discrete wavelet transform] decomposes a time series into components that are localized in time and frequency by performing a number of convolutions between a time series and dilations/contractions of a function called mother wavelet. Since each wavelet (i.e., each dilation and contraction of the mother wavelet) represents a different frequency interval in the frequency domain, wavelets are comparable to bandpass filters” (2022:3). Cross-wavelet transform analysis, in which two wavelet transforms are combined, has proved an effective tool with which to explore coordination between individuals (see e.g., Clayton et al. 2019, Toivianen & Hartmann 2022). In this analysis we use wavelet transforms of the instrumental onset data in order to extract information about the music's periodic structure.

9. Semi-structured interviews were conducted individually so each musician's comments would not be influenced by those of their peers. Time codes in the published transcripts are given in the text. In the case of supplementary personal communications with the musicians outside of the recorded interviews, references include the date.

with the other instruments the *shō* player memorizes the details of a *jobuki* piece using *shōga* mnemonics of both the *hichiriki* and the *shō* before playing it (Yatsuki 00:22:42). It is remarkable that other musicians also refer to both initiative (as in “establishing” one’s own style) and reactivity (as in “coping” with what others play). However, the *hichiriki* player Miura and the *ryūteki* player Kōketsu appear more conscious of the need to show their independence to the other parts, by clearly demonstrating the “*katachi* (lit. form)” they have acquired (Miura 00:50:13, Kōketsu 00:28:34). Regarding the wind instruments, then, there is an emphasis on each instrument’s independence, but at the same time an awareness that this places a greater load on the musicians to follow and respond to other players.

[20] Notably, the presence of order and intention behind *jobuki*, which is not based on the metrical-formal structure, was highlighted. Kōketsu describes this as the point of convergence where the “form” of each part moves together, i.e. when the *taiko* enters, only then does “beat” or “order” occur instantaneously (00:28:34). (The *taiko* has an important role in marking the long cycles in metrical pieces, and—as we will see—also in marking the structure of some of the *jobuki* pieces.) Miura also points out that, even up to this convergence point, there is a kind of “regularity” between the *hichiriki* and *ryūteki* (00:51:49): when the melody of the *hichiriki* starts moving, the melody of the *ryūteki* also starts moving, and when the *ryūteki* plays a technique *hataku* 叩 <¹⁰, the melody of the *hichiriki* also moves. Through such complex synchronicities, “a chaotic world is deliberately created” (Miura 00:55:08). The comment suggests that one clue to understanding the melodic progression is to listen to the detailed playing techniques of the other winds. This is more or less true of metrical pieces as well, but the musicians emphasize that there is a lot of detailed interaction between the *hichiriki* and the *ryūteki* in *jobuki* pieces, with each waiting to hear the other’s note before moving on to the next note.

[21] In contrast to the detailed comments on the wind parts, very little was said in the interviews about the string and percussion parts in *jobuki*. One of the reasons for this seems to be that the position of the string and percussion parts in the ensemble also seems to differ considerably from that of the metrical pieces. According to Miura, in *jobuki*—in

10. Known as “*tataku*” or “*hataku*” (both literally meaning “tapping”). This is an ornamental technique for a sustained note, in which one fingerhole is lightly tapped to produce an adjacent lower note momentarily.

contrast to the metrical pieces—the wind players in the back row rarely consciously observe the arm movements of the *biwa* and *taiko*. Rather, he said, both string and percussion parts need to be fully aware of the wind phrases in order to insert patterns as they progress (personal communication, 11 September 2023).

[22] In *jobuki*, the *biwa* and *koto* parts are defined in terms of the amount of material that should be played between each *taiko* point; however, the amount they are required to play in each *taiko* interval is not constant, which means that some spans feel rhythmically dense while others are sparse. Performers find that fitting the required material into the allotted span requires careful attention, especially when the rhythmic density varies considerably. Whereas in metrical pieces they work together to mark the beat position, in *jobuki*, the *biwa* and *koto* parts are less coordinated—except at the *taiko* point. It is stated that the *koto* is rarely taken into account by the other instruments, and that the musicians themselves may find that some *koto* passages contain too many notes. In percussion, complex patterns on the *kakko* are added to the performance based on the ‘*katashi* 形 (lit. form or shape)’ created by the winds, and finally the *taiko* and the subsequent *shōko* enter (personal communication, 11 September 2023). The deliberate matching at the *taiko* point in *jobuki* (Kōketsu 00:28:34) does not seem to be limited to the winds, and seems to be an increased awareness of “moving towards the convergence point” throughout the ensemble. It should be noted, however, that the above statements are about *kangen* instrumental performance; in the case of *bugaku* dance accompaniment, musicians have to respond to the dancer’s movement timing, for example by playing longer up to a certain *taiko* point where there is a lot of dance movement in between.

[23] What emerges from the musicians’ comments is that the absence of a metrical framework further increases the need for the three wind instruments to understand and cooperate with each other’s detailed playing, and for strings and percussion to participate in the ensemble based on the winds’ phrase progression. So, what aspects of timing and coordination can be found empirically in *jobuki*? Let us now turn to the results of the analysis of audiovisual data.

Event Plots

[24] It is difficult to approach the task of analyzing the time organization of the *jobuki* sections given the absence of a metrical structure. However, given the pieces are composed—and repeatable with a high degree of similarity—it is possible to describe

their formal structure by observing occurrences of repeated or similar material (which are also observable in the performers' notation). The distribution of musical events performed by the various instruments can be visualized by plotting the annotation data acquired using the methods described above, and this can enable us to explore the relationships between parts. This approach has some advantages compared with traditional transcription-based approaches: in the latter it is possible to observe melodic detail, but this information tends to obscure the temporal relationships between different instruments. This is also the case for the performers' notation. Subtle beat stretching and contraction are not documented in their written notation, although they can be observed in the performers' *shōga*-singing practice.¹¹ It can be said that rhythmic details, including deliberate asynchrony with other parts, are acquired as embodied knowledge for the performers and not something to be documented in a fixed form.

[25] Event plots are created in RStudio using annotation data relating to the structure (e.g., sections divided into 'Sentences'; wind phrase start and end points; and rhythmic events or 'onsets'). Fig. 5 illustrates the first A section of the *jobuki* Tesshō. From top to bottom, this plot visualizes the following information:

- i. The section is divided into three sub-sections or Sentences, of which the longest is the middle one, a2 (figures in blue indicate the duration in seconds)
- ii. Of the wind instruments, the *ryūteki* starts first; once the *hichiriki* joins in, their phrases are roughly aligned with each other.
- iii. Pairs of *taiko* strokes (dark blue), each followed by *shōko* strokes (green), mark the ends of Sentences.
- iv. The accelerating patterns of the *kakko*, marked in grey, indicate another division of the sentences which is not always closely aligned with the wind phrases.

11. An oral mnemonic system known as *shōga* 唱歌 (literally meaning "singing song") is an indispensable means for grasping the melodic details and the flow of the music as a whole, as a musician's learning process begins with *shōga* in one of the wind instruments.

- v. Plucks on the *biwa* (pink) and *koto* (orange) punctuate the second and third sentences; their alignment with or relationship to the other parts and with each other is not immediately obvious.

Tessho (take 1)

Structure

Figure 5. Visual representation of the first A section of the piece Tesshō (take 1). The top row ('Structure') shows the structural division into Sentences; the next two rows the extents of the phrases of *hichiriki* and *ryūteki* (all with times in seconds written in blue). The fourth row shows the strokes of the percussion instruments (*kakko* in grey, *taiko* blue, *shōko* green). The bottom row shows the plucks of the string instruments (*biwa* in pink, *koto* in orange).

Figure 6. Visual representation of a part of the piece *Juha*. Key as Figure 5.

[26] If we compare this with a section of the metrical piece *Juha* (Fig. 6), in the latter case we see much more regularity. For example, the sentence *b1* can be divided symmetrically into two halves at around 225 secs; the *shōko* strokes (green) divide the duration between the second *taiko* stroke (blue) into three parts; the *biwa* strokes (pink) are aligned with those of the *taiko* and *shōko*; and so on. In short, we can see on this plot how the strings and percussion mark out the metrical structure, with a regularity that is not present in the *jobuki* piece *Tesshō*.

[27] As is summarized in Table 2 above, these plots show how each piece in the suite, whether metrical or *jobuki*, features a clear structure, including the repetition of one or more sections. In terms of temporal durations, this hierarchical structure in *jobuki* pieces looks roughly as follows (timings for *Jo* are given separately as the scale is rather greater than the other pieces):

“*Jo*”:

Piece (15 mins) > Sections (3–4 min) > Sentences (35–75 secs) > Phrases (3–13 secs)

“*Yūsei*,” “*Tesshō*,” “*Kisshō*” final section:

Piece (5 mins) > Sections (40–80 secs) > Sentences (14–30 secs) > Phrases (3–13 secs)

[28] Since we have two takes each of Yūsei and Tesshō we can compare the timings and distribution of events between takes to get an idea of the reproducibility of the the *jobuki* pieces' temporal structure. Here (Figs 7 and 8) we take as an example the first B section of “Yūsei.”

Figure 7. Visual representation of a part of the piece Yūsei (take 1). Key as Figure 5.

Figure 8. Visual representation of a part of the piece Yūsei (take 2). Key as Figure 5.

[29] The two plots are clearly very similar, reflecting a high degree of alignment between two takes of the same piece. The section is divided into two sentences of approximately 20 secs each, divided into 2 and 3 wind phrases respectively, with the two instruments closely aligned. The durations are similar, but there appears to be some flexibility: the first wind phrase is somewhat longer in take 1 than take 2.¹² The *kakko* part is divided into three phrases with different characteristics (each accelerating, but with different profiles). The *biwa* plucks are fairly evenly distributed, while the *koto* is sparser during the second wind phrase. The alignment between the instrument groups shows more differences between takes. The first *kakko* pattern ends during the second wind phrase and the second *kakko* pattern in the third wind phrase, for example, but they overlap considerably more in take 2 than take 1. The string parts are distributed similarly in the two takes and appear to be aligned with the winds rather than the *kakko* (given the melodic element this is logical); where there is inconsistency between the takes it is in the alignment between the *biwa* and *koto* (in some cases the two strokes fall close together on one take but not on the other).

[30] Similar features can be observed in the other *jobuki* sections (for a complete set of plots see the Appendix). They suggest the following observations about the structure and ensemble coordination.

- Wind phrases are closely aligned between the two instruments; the *hichiriki* tends to start fractionally before and end fractionally after the *ryūteki*. (There are a few exceptions: sometimes a single phrase in one corresponds to two phrases in the other.)
- Percussion. As we can see in the first plot, the *taiko*, where present, marks the end of sentences with a double stroke; the *shōko* strokes are closely aligned with the *taiko*. The *kakko* has its own sequence of patterns that divide up the sections; although these often align roughly with the wind phrases, they may overlap the latter significantly. Faster or denser patterns tend to occur at the start of Sentences.
- String phrases. Both *biwa* and *koto* parts relate to the wind phrases, although their precise temporal relationship to the rest of the group, and to each other, is not obvious. In metrical pieces where the strings indicate the beat, their onsets often

12. Hichiriki: 8.1 vs 7.5 secs (8.5% longer in take 1); ryūteki, 7.9 vs 6.8 secs (15.8%).

fall alongside those of the *taiko* and other percussion (Fig. 6). In *jobuki*, however, with the exception of the *taiko* point, the temporal relationship with the percussion becomes less clear. In particular, in *Yūsei* (Figs. 7 and 8), which was used as an example of reproducibility, the only percussion instrument is *kakko*, but the string parts seem to add the same ‘fixed number of notes’ to it in the two takes, using the wind instrument phrase rather than the *kakko* as a cue. This is also consistent with statements made in interviews.

[31] Having made some basic observations about the relationships between parts of the ensemble, we now explore the temporal characteristics of the different parts to search for evidence of temporal regularities: recurring phrase lengths or intervals between rhythmic events.

Wind Phrase Durations

[32] In the *Tesshō* plots introduced above we can observe that the final phrase of each sentence tends to last around 6–6.5 secs¹³; these wind phrases are essentially the same, so this temporal regularity is simply a result of the repetition of melodic material. For the parts of the *hichiriki* and *ryūteki*, the following analysis compares the wind phrase durations across each piece, both metrical and *jobuki* sections. We can get a more comprehensive view of the wind phrase durations by plotting them against time for all of the pieces (Fig. 9). This shows a clear difference between the *jobuki* (*Yūsei*, *Jo*, *Tesshō*, *Kisshō_jb*) and the metrical pieces (*Sattō*, *Juha* and *Kisshō_m*)¹⁴ In the latter we see a clear pattern, which is especially clear in the *hichiriki* parts: there are two clear lines of decreasing duration, matching the acceleration of these pieces. In the *jobuki* pieces on the other hand there is no visible pattern of acceleration, although in *Tesshō* we can a line reflecting see the consistent durations around 6 secs noted above.

13. *Hichiriki*, mean = 6.55 secs, SD 1.30; *ryūteki*, mean 6.21 secs, SD 0.84 (*Tesshō* take 1).

14. In these figures *kisshō_m* refers to the metrical part and *kisshō_jb* to the *jobuki* part of the same piece, respectively.

Figure 9. Wind phrase durations of all pieces. *Jobuki* sections are highlighted. The metrical and *jobuki* parts of Kisshō are plotted separately (7_Kissho_m the metrical, 7_Kissho_jb the *jobuki*).

[33] The boxplot of wind phrase durations (Fig. 10) shows clearly that the mean lengths are lower for the metrical pieces Sattō and Juha (although less so for Kisshō) than for the *jobuki* pieces (mean 5.65 +/- 2.14 secs for metrical vs 8.04 +/- 2.7 secs for *jobuki* sections). *Hichiriki* phrases are on average a little longer than *Ryūteki* for all pieces (mean 7.57 vs 6.92 secs).

[34] A further observation on the wind phrases is that the proportion of the total time in which these instruments are playing is lower in the metrical sections (82%) than the *jobuki* (91%). In other words, they rest for a longer proportion of time in the metrical sections (Table 3, see Appendix).

Figure 10. Boxplot of wind phrase durations for all pieces. Horizontal lines indicate the mean durations. Jobuki sections are highlighted. The metrical and jobuki parts of Kisshō are plotted separately (7_Kissho_m the metrical, 7_Kissho_jb the jobuki)

[35] This analysis of the wind phrases shows a clear distinction between metrical and *jobuki* sections. In the metrical sections (especially Sattō and Juha), we see a

predominance of two duration classes and an accelerating pattern – both of which phenomena are related to the metrical structure – and these instruments rest up to 20% of the time. In the *jobuki* sections, there is neither acceleration nor a bimodal distribution of durations, and the resting time is less than 10%: in *Tesshō*, however, a frequently repeated phrase gives rise to a predominant phrase duration of around 6 secs, which is observed at the end of Sentences. The mean phrase duration is longer in the *jobuki* sections and is longer for *hichiriki* than *ryūteki* in all pieces.

[36] This seems to suggest that while the melodic content of the wind phrases is similar between *jobuki* and metrical pieces, their duration is constrained by the metrical structure articulated by the strings and percussion – which dictates that they must end, or reach a point of emphasis, by a specific point in time. This would also explain the longer pauses between wind phrases: the wind players enter the next phrase only after the appropriate point in the metrical structure that is created by all the parts, whereas they have more independence in relation to the progression of the *jobuki* pieces.

ONSET INTERVALS

Onset Intervals by Instrument

[37] In this next stage of analysis, we look for evidence of consistency of time intervals (inter-onset intervals, IOIs) in the onset data, again comparing metrical and *jobuki* sections. To do this, we select onsets for each instrument in the string and percussion sections, and calculate the intervals between successive events. Since we are interested only in intervals likely to have a rhythmic significance, we discard intervals over 6 seconds. It is clear from Fig. 11 that the *kakko* and *shōko* intervals tend to be shorter (median 175 and 130 ms respectively), the *koto* favours a medium interval (median = 1015 ms) and the *biwa* and *taiko* have longer intervals (medians 3414 and 3195 respectively). We now explore the patterns of onset differences by instrument, comparing also the metrical and *jobuki* pieces.

Figure 11. Histogram of inter-onset intervals up to 6 seconds for wind and percussion instruments (plotted with a log scale to avoid it being distorted by the higher numbers of *kakko* onsets than the other instruments). Vertical dashed lines are computed median values for each instrument.

Taiko

[38] As already noted, in *jobuki* pieces where it is used, the *taiko* is generally used to mark the ends of Sentences; in metrical pieces, it also marks significant points in the metrical structure. The common pattern is a pair of strokes – a left-hand strike followed by a louder right-hand strike – although variations with additional strokes, known as *kuwaebiyoshi* 加拍子, may be observed in the latter part of the piece. Fig. 12 shows the intervals between these pairs of strokes. Of the *jobuki* pieces, in Jo these gaps range between 3.5–4.5 secs, showing a slight trend to shorten; in Tesshō they are between 3–4 secs and lengthen towards the end. In the metrical pieces, these intervals range between 2.5–4 secs with an accelerating trend; in Kisshō (on the plot, the second, unhighlighted part of 6_Tessho_2), which uses a different pattern of *taiko* strokes, there are two accelerating lines and an overall range of intervals between 1.5–4 secs.

[39] Overall while the *taiko* intervals in the metrical pieces reflect their metrical structure, the intervals in the *jobuki* sections cover a similar range with either no (Tesshō) or more limited (Jo) acceleration. In the latter case, since the intervals are around 3 secs or above and are single intervals interspersed with much longer gaps, rather than a sequence of similar intervals, there is no possibility that they could in themselves generate a sense of periodicity.

Figure 12. Inter-onset intervals for the *taiko*. Left pane: all IOIs (in seconds) up to 5 secs plotted against time, separately for each piece. *Jobuki* sections are highlighted. Right pane: histogram of all IOIs across the corpus under 5 secs.

Shōko

[40] The *shōko* strikes are closely linked to the *taiko*'s. The plot of all intervals (Fig. 13) shows the different patterns used in each piece, and also the clear acceleration in the metrical pieces, which is evident in the longer intervals. In the shorter intervals between pairs of *shōko* strikes we see little variation or acceleration, although the range is somewhat slower in the *jobuki* than it is in the metrical pieces. These isolated, short IOIs would not be expected to afford a metrical perception.

Figure 13. Inter-onset intervals for the *shōko*. Left pane: all IOIs plotted against time, separately for each piece (intervals in secs). Right pane: histogram of all IOIs under 200 ms, illustrating the clustering around 100–150 ms

Kakko

[41] The chart for the *kakko* onset intervals (Fig. 14) shows that the patterns are similar in each piece, comprising accelerating sequences with different gradients. Zooming in to the first 180 secs of each piece these patterns become clearer.¹⁵ It does not seem plausible that this pattern could induce a sense of meter, given the constantly changing intervals involved; there are differences between the deployment of the patterns by piece, but not such a clear difference between metrical and *jobuki* categories.

15. One-handed techniques are referred to as “katarai” and double-handed techniques as “mororai.” It is difficult to annotate these in Figure 14, however, as there is often a transition from mororai to katarai and vice versa in the middle of a pattern.

Figure 14. Inter-onset intervals for the *kakko*. Left pane: all IOIs below 1 sec plotted against time, separately for each piece (intervals in secs). Right pane: the same data, showing up to 150 secs only to make the different acceleration patterns clearer

Biwa

[42] Turning now to the string section, the *biwa* onsets show a clear difference between the metrical and *jobuki* pieces (Fig. 15). In the former, Sattō, Juha and Kisshō show lines reflecting two interval ranges, which accelerate gradually through the pieces. This is not surprising, since many *biwa* onsets fall on beats 1 or 3 of the measure and given that these pieces speed up. The *jobuki* pieces show a more normal (rather than bi-modal)

distribution, peaking between 2.5–5 secs. Again, IOIs in this range are unlikely to give rise to a perception of a regular beat.

Figure 15. Inter-onset intervals for the *biwa*. Left pane: all IOIs below 15 secs plotted against time, separately for each piece (intervals in secs). Right pane: histogram of all IOIs under 12.5 secs, separately for each piece

Koto

[43] The *koto* plots (Fig. 16) again show a clear difference between metrical and *jobuki* pieces: the latter show a preponderance of intervals around 1 sec, while the former seem to be more structured, with many intervals in the 2–7 sec range. The peak of the distribution in all cases is below 1 sec, however. According to the musicians, in the

metrical sections the *koto* has the role of “clearly indicating the beats” (as noted in the Introduction), whereas in *jobuki* it “puts in a set number of notes” as appropriate to each wind phrase. In the latter case, it is stated that the musicians themselves may find some passages contain too many notes (see Interviews). In other words, this part in *jobuki* shows the most consistently fine note values among the percussion and string sections, but this does not necessarily create a sense of beat shared by the whole ensemble and may have more of an ornamental function in relation to the wind phrases.

Figure 16. Inter-onset intervals for the *koto*. Left pane: all IOIs below 20 secs plotted against time, separately for each piece (intervals in secs). Right pane: histogram of all IOIs under 5 secs, separately for each piece

Combined Onset Periodicity Analysis

[44] In the onset data for individual instruments, we have seen some evidence for consistent time intervals, for example around 1 and around 3 secs, even in *jobuki* pieces. These could in principle be related to a sense of beat or metrical structure, although there is no evidence that they are consistent enough for this to happen. We should not assume, however, that cues for metrical perception (such as regular time intervals between rhythmic events) are found only in the patterns of single instruments. Indeed, in Kamata & Clayton 2025, we showed how the percussion and string instruments combine together to mark out the metrical structures. In order to look for such metricity in combinations of instruments we use a different method, however (since simple differencing across the full set of onset times would bias the analysis to very small, insignificant intervals).

[45] We devised the following method to explore evidence of periodicity in combinations of instruments. All onsets are combined into a single CSV file per piece (in this case *ryūteki* and *hichiriki* are also included, with moments of clear pitch change marked as ‘onsets’ as they could be treated as rhythmic events). This data is converted into a histogram (i.e., a count of the number of onsets per time unit, in this case 100ms).¹⁶ The resulting time series is analyzed using wavelet transforms to reveal its periodic structure.

[46] For example, in the metrical piece Sattō, Fig. 17a shows the all-onset histogram for measures 9–24 inclusive, with the metrical downbeats shown in red for reference (the main *taiko* strokes fall on points 15 and 23). Many of the onset histogram peaks lie close to the metrical downbeats, which reflects the fact that multiple instruments tend to play close together at these moments. The plot of total wavelet energy against time for this section is shown in Fig. 17b, and the wavelet plot showing the distribution of energy across periodicities in Fig. 17c. For the same section Fig. 17d summarises the wavelet energy across different periods between 0.5 and 10 secs, which shows four peaks (the red dots indicate statistical significance, $p < 0.05$). These peaks (0.90, 1.93, 4.00 and 8.00 secs) clearly correspond to the metrical levels in the piece at this point (the ½-beat, beat, 2-beat and measure levels; the mean beat length calculated from manual meter annotations for this section is 2.08 secs, with a range of 1.76-2.42 secs across the measures). These results

16. Comparison with bin sizes of 20ms and 50ms revealed no significant differences in the result.

are not surprising – we already know the metrical structure – but they demonstrate that by using this method, the hierarchical structure that makes up the meter is recoverable from the onset times. If a similar pattern were to be observed in the *jobuki* sections, it could suggest the possibility that a metrical structure may be perceptible.

[47] Comparing the wavelet energy plots shows up a clear difference between the metrical and *jobuki* sections (Jo and Sattō are compared in Fig. 18 – the other movements are included in the Appendix). In Sattō, Juha, and Kisshō (excepting the last section of Kisshō, which is *jobuki*), the wavelet energy is concentrated in a set of clear lines of gradually reducing periodicity, which is not the case in the *jobuki* pieces: these lines correspond to the different metrical levels as the piece accelerates (see Table 4). What is clear from the peak periods is that they lie very close to a hierarchical pattern (in Sattō and Juha, in the ratio 1:2:4:8); comparison with the calculated mean beat length shows the fastest or second-fastest level to be close to the beat¹⁷. We can also see a variation in energy levels as we look along the time (x) axis: the peaks here correspond to the metrical downbeats, when instruments tend to play together. In the *jobuki* pieces, on the other hand, no such patterns are visible in the periodicity of the areas of higher energy (y-axis); this is confirmed when we compare the peak periods across the pieces with two takes each, Yūsei and Tesshō. In this case the results look quite different between takes, even if there are points of similarity in some sections (see Table 5). There does however appear to be a clear similarity between the energy vs time plots for different takes of the same *jobuki* piece, even if these are not reflected in robust periodicities which might have indicated the emergence of a beat or metrical structure. This can be seen comparing plots of total wavelet energy against time for the two takes of Tesshō (see Fig. 19¹⁸): there is a clear similarity in the distribution of wavelet energy peaks in relation to the structural markers, even if the relative height of the peaks varies significantly. As with the metrical pieces, the tendency for structural markers to coincide with wavelet energy peaks in the onset data is a reflection of the tendency for more instruments to ‘converge’ and play close together near the *taiko* strokes.

17. The fact that the mean beat duration and the shortest period in the wavelet analysis do not coincide exactly is not surprising, given the much more complex mathematics used to calculate the latter (the Mean beat length is simple average of the means for each measure in the section).

¹⁸ While the figures given in the tables, and the wavelet energy plots, are based on analysis of the data with a period range of 0.5–8 secs, for these figures the range has been set to 2–8 secs to improve readability.

Figure 17. Wavelet analysis of Sattō, measures 9–24 inclusive. Panel a shows the all-onset histogram for this section. Panel b plots the total wavelet energy against time for the same section. In both cases metrical boundaries are indicated with red vertical lines. Panel c is a wavelet plot showing the distribution of energy across periodicities (0.5 to 10 secs). Panel d summarises the wavelet energy across different periods between 0.5 and 10 secs.

Piece	Section	Wavelet peak periods (secs)	Mean beat length (secs)
Sattō	A	0.87**, 1.87**, 3.86**, 7.27**	2.05
	B	0.76**, 1.52**, 3.14**, 6.28**	1.59
	C	0.68**, 1.41**, 2.83**, 5.86**	1.44
	B'	0.64**, 1.27**, 2.64**, 5.28**	1.32
Juha	A	0.76**, 1.57**, 3.36**, 6.96**	1.87
	B	0.66**, 1.37**, 2.83**, 5.66**	1.44
	C	0.62**, 1.27**, 2.64**, 5.28**	1.33
	B'	0.57**, 1.19**, 2.38**, 4.92**	1.24
Kisshō	A	0.55**, 1.03**, 2.22**	1.28
	B	0.93**, 1.87**, 3.86(ns)	0.95
	C	0.84**, 1.68**, 3.48**	0.87
	B'	0.78**, 1.62**, 3.25(ns)	0.8

Table 4. Peak periods of wavelet energy vs mean beat length. Wavelet analysis carried out for range 0.5–8 secs. (** p<.05)

Piece	Section	Take 1: Wavelet peak periods (secs)	Take 2: Wavelet peak periods (secs)
Yūsei	A	0.76**, 1.62*, 3.36**	3.6*
	B	0.55*, 0.87**	0.84**, 1.32*
	C	n/a	1.80*
	B	0.61**, 1.37*	0.59*, 0.90*
	C	1.87*	3.30**, 1.19*
	B	1.46**	0.59**, 1.18*
Tesshō	A	0.52**, 1.07**	1.23*
	A'	0.52**	0.55**, 2.92**
	A''	0.52**, 1.07**	1.11**
	A'''	0.52*, 1.04**	0.66**
	B	0.66**	0.55**, 4.59*

Table 5. Comparison of wavelet energy peak periods between takes of Yūsei and Tesshō. Wavelet analysis carried out for range 0.5–8 secs. (* $p < .1$, ** $p < .05$)

Figure 18. Jo and Sattō, plots of wavelet energy against time for all onset data (plots for all movements are included in the Appendix). Sattō, the metrical movement, shows the emergence of clear bands of periodicity and a pattern of acceleration as these periods become shorter.

Figure 19. Plots of total wavelet energy against time for all onsets, comparing the two takes of Tesshō. Section boundaries are shown in red.

Summary

[48] In this section we have explored the onset timing data, searching for possible indications of regular beat or metrical structures in the *jobuki* sections. Instead we find a clear distinction between the metrical and *jobuki* parts: in the former the event structure as evidenced by the combined onsets clearly marks out the metrical structure, while in the latter, periodicities seem to emerge – as shown by the wavelet analysis which shows statistically significant energy peaks at certain periods in most sections – but they are not sustained, and nor are they generally replicated between takes. There is evidence of particular IOIs being favored for specific instruments: for example, around 1 second for *koto* and 3 seconds for *biwa* and *taiko*. This could be linked to the timing of particular playing movements: the carefully controlled and stylized nature of the preparatory movements of *taiko*, *shōko*, *biwa* and *koto* may help to fix the timing of certain passages within a narrow range. This does not, however, seem to generate a sense of beat or metrical structure.

DISCUSSION

[49] As outlined in Kamata & Clayton 2025, metrical pieces in this dataset display a clear hierarchical time structure, from beat through measure and *taiko* cycle to Sections and whole pieces. The music is characterized by slow but gradually accelerating tempo, by an extended final beat, and by very loose synchronization. The metrical structure is unambiguously marked out by string and percussion instruments, each of which has its own individual role. In *jobuki* pieces we hear a superficially similar musical surface, but the metrical level of the time organization is not present, and thus neither is the gradual acceleration. (Since there are few instances when all instruments are expected to coincide, it is not possible to quantify ‘synchronization’.) Yet these composed pieces are reproducible with a high degree of similarity, and display a clear formal hierarchy of phrases, Sentences and Sections, with *taiko* and *shōko* typically marking the ends of Sentences. The coordination of strings and percussion to articulate a metrical structure is not present in *jobuki* pieces: their gestures, without metrical significance, can be heard more as articulating and supporting the melodic content presented by the wind section.

[50] One way of helping us understand the unmetred form of *gagaku* is to summarize what meter *does* when present. As we have seen in this analysis, meter has a strong impact on the wind phrases: we can think of the melodic gestures as being embodied with a

natural duration which is revealed in the *jobuki* pieces, while in the metrical piece a common frame with subtle acceleration is put in place. Strings and percussion instruments play the role of indicators in this common frame, i.e., the metrical cycle. In *jobuki* pieces, described by interviewees as showing more independence, the winds play their phrases and take relatively short breaths, but in metrical forms they may naturally compress phrases or take longer pauses to maintain the ensemble coordination. In *jobuki* pieces, the need to stay coordinated with the wind phrases is an important constraint on the timing of strings and percussion. The stability of the phrases means that we do see some consistency in IOIs across pieces, rather than IOIs related to the meter which shorten as the piece accelerates.

[51] In the *jobuki*, then, wind phrases mark out the melodic progressions and combine to form Sentences, Sections and pieces. The length of these phrases depends mostly on their melodic content, and there is no acceleration through a piece. *Hichiriki* and *ryūteki* phrases are closely aligned with each other. The *shō*, an essential wind instrument, could not be included in the empirical analysis based on ‘onsets’, but the interview results highlighted the fact that performers could not play the part without a detailed understanding of the relationships between the winds. *Taiko* strokes, where present, mark the ends of Sentences, and *shōko* strokes closely follow the *taiko*, but *kakko* patterns also divide up the Sentences, being loosely coordinated with the wind phrases. *Biwa* and *koto* patterns punctuate or decorate the melody but in terms of timing are not coordinated with each other or with the percussion. Each has its own loose preferred periodicity. In short, our empirical analysis has elaborated the picture described by the musicians, in which each player has a relatively high degree of independence, but each must concentrate hard to maintain the coherence of the ensemble without relying on a metrical timing structure.

[52] Even in metrical pieces, subtle gestures and phrases of all instruments are combined, and one can feel a sound world which is superficially similar to the *jobuki* music. In this case, however, the emphasis is placed on all the parts working together to create a gradually accelerating metrical grid. As a result, the wind phrases no longer display the same level of independence as in *jobuki*, as they often have to end, or reach a point of emphasis, to coincide with a metrical event. As the metrical grid accelerates gradually, the wind phrases also become compressed.

[53] As we have seen in the analysis, it is not the case that the *jobuki* music is completely without periodic elements: we have observed these in various instrumental gestures. Whereas in metrical music such periodicities tend to be sustained and align with each other, through entrainment, to produce beat and meter, in these *jobuki* pieces they remain intermittent and largely limited to single instruments. We know from the entrainment literature that mutual attention tends to lead to entrainment, even when not intended; we also know that visual attention can be an important contributory factor (e.g., Richardson et al., 2005; Lucas et al 2011); we also know, however, that people's ability to synchronize with periodic rhythms drops with intervals over about 2 seconds (Repp & Doggett 2007). We may hypothesize then that the successful avoidance, or management, of entrainment in this case relates to two factors: the management of attention and the control of time intervals. As for the first, the musicians are clearly paying great attention to each other. However, focusing more on the long continuous gestures of the winds rather than the *koto* phrases, for example, may limit the likelihood of falling into a regular beat. For the latter, many of the key time intervals used to structure the music – the wind phrases, the intervals between *biwa* or *taiko* striking gestures for example – are well over 2 seconds, while the faster intervals of the *kakko* are never stable (they always accelerate). The music seems almost to have been designed to limit the possibility of accidentally falling into a metrical pattern. This idea recalls the emphasis in the interviews on the “order” and “intention” behind *jobuki*.

[54] Hasty's idea of projection is concerned with the possibility that a listener evaluates the duration of musical events with reference to previous durations (1997). Roeder has shown how this idea may be applied to a wide variety of free rhythm, monophonic musical examples, and how variations in duration may be an integral part of wider musical processes (2019). Applying this to *jobuki* is not straightforward for two reasons: first, that we are discussing ensemble music, and second, that the music is composed and reproducible. As for the first, this may not be insurmountable, since the wind phrases as performed on *hichiriki* and *ryūteki* are closely aligned in both melodic content and duration. As for the second, any sensation related to a particular phrase being longer or shorter than the preceding one must factor in – for the experienced listener or co-performer – the fact that such phenomena are highly expected; we might reasonably ask whether the durations are being compared to the previous phrase or to prior knowledge of the current phrase. For this reason, we hesitate to extend Roeder's application of projection to these examples. However, it is clear that the tracking of phrases, and of

events such as ornaments or pitch changes within phrases while they are ongoing, is key to the experience of the musicians, and that these musicians must have a well-practiced memory of the typical duration of the phrases.

[55] What the music presents is a complex whole made up of continuously trackable durations – phrases and preparatory movements – and events that punctuate those durations without generating metrical expectations. An observation that may have wider applicability is that unmetered group coordination may be easier when the whole group takes its cue from the timing of irregular wind phrases. Other instruments produce sharper attacks and are more likely to spontaneously develop beat and meter, but they are constrained by their dependence on the wind phrases; the latter offer continuous melodic trajectories of over 3 seconds that may give rise to a form of projection but not to a consistent entrained beat structure. This paper has described a form of unmetered time organization in composed ensemble music and proposed an interpretation of the processes that allow such organization to be sustained and reproduced. There is no doubt more to be discovered about this type of time organization, both in *tōgaku* and in other genres which may be comparable in this respect.

APPENDIX: INTERVIEWEE BIOGRAPHIES

Motonori Miura has been familiar with *gagaku* since his childhood and was taught to play the *hichiriki* by his father Susumu Miura. He further studied *hichiriki* and court songs under Masasue Tōgi, *umai* dance under Tadaaki Ōno (both from the Music Department of the Imperial Household Agency), and received a Bachelor of Music degree in *gagaku* performance from the Tokyo University of the Arts in 2005. Miura is a member of Tokyo Gakuso, a professional *gagaku* group, and belongs to Pro Musica Nipponia, the Naoyuki MANABE GAGAKU Ensemble, Ensemble Muromachi, and the GAGAKU Association, and has been performing in Japan and abroad for 20 years. In addition to performing traditional repertoire, his activities include world premieres of contemporary works, music supervision of stage productions, recordings, media appearances and productions. Miura was an Adjunct Instructor at Tokyo University of the Arts from 2015 to 2023 and continues to teach younger students.

Born into a family of Shinto priests serving the Tsutsukowake Shrine in Tanagura, Fukushima Prefecture, Junko Yatsuki was introduced to *gagaku*. She studied *shō* under Tadaaki Ōno, court songs under Masasue Tōgi, *samai* dance under Takaaki Iwanami and

Seiichi Masuyama, and *koto* under Seiichi Masuyama (all from the Music Department of the Imperial Household Agency), and received a Bachelor of Music degree in *gagaku* performance from the Tokyo University of the Arts in 2010. Yatsuki is a member of Tokyo Gakuso, a professional *gagaku* group, and has been performing in Japan and abroad for over 15 years. As a member of the Shinto priesthood, she is also committed to the transmission of *gagaku* as ritual music. At her alma mater, Tokyo University of the Arts, Yatsuki was an Education and Research Assistant from 2013 to 2023 and an Adjunct Instructor from 2015 to 2023 and continues to teach younger students.

Takuya Kōketsu studied *ryūteki* under Kenji Ue, Takaaki Iwanami, and Chiaki Yagi, court songs under Seiichi Masuyama, and *umai* dance under Tadaaki Ōno and Hokuto Matsui. He graduated with a Bachelor of Music degree in *gagaku* performance from Tokyo University of the Arts in 2014 and was awarded the Acanthus Music Prize. In addition to being a member of the professional group Tokyo Gakuso, Kōketsu has performed on the recordings and world tours of Tim Hecker's "KONOYO" and "ANOYO," "Yuzuru Hanyu Programme Concert - Music with Wings," the anime "The Tale of the Heike" (Fuji TV), the historical dramas "Kamakura-dono no jūsan-nin," "Dousuru Ieyasu," "Hikaru-kimi" (NHK), "Monster Hunter Rise" and the 50th anniversary of the establishment of Japanese diplomatic relations in the UAE, among others. At Tokyo University of the Arts, he has been training younger students as an Education and Research Assistant since 2016 and as an Adjunct Instructor since 2024.

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